

Application of OpenMC for generation of the few-group cross-section library for full core SMR analysis

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ABSTRACT

Accurate modelling and simulation of Small Modular Reactor (SMR) cores are essential for assessing reactor performance across a range of operating conditions. Monte Carlo (MC) transport methods, such as those implemented in OpenMC, provide high-fidelity neutronic solutions but require considerable computational resources. Deterministic codes like DYN3D offer significantly reduced computational costs, making them more suitable for routine engineering and operational applications, provided that their cross-section data are generated with sufficient accuracy. In this work, a NuScale-like SMR core model was developed and simulated using the DYN3D code. The cross-section library required for the deterministic calculations was generated using OpenMC, establishing a workflow that integrates high-fidelity MC transport with efficient nodal diffusion reactor analysis. Comparative assessments were conducted between OpenMC and DYN3D results, with emphasis on reactivity coefficients and assembly power distributions. The differences observed between the two approaches indicate the influence of homogenization and spectral effects on deterministic accuracy. Future work will investigate improvements such as B1 spectral correction and Assembly Discontinuity Factors (ADFs) to enhance cross-section consistency and overall predictive capability for SMR core simulations.

Keywords: NuScale; SMR; OpenMC; DYN3D; Monte Carlo

1. INTRODUCTION

Small Modular Reactors (SMRs) are increasingly recognized as a promising source of clean and flexible nuclear energy, offering enhanced safety and scalability for future power systems [1,2]. Accurate modeling and simulation are essential for optimizing SMR core design and ensuring operational safety under various conditions [3].

Monte Carlo (MC) transport methods, such as OpenMC [4], provide high-fidelity neutronic solutions by explicitly representing complex reactor geometries and detailed energy spectra. However, their high computational cost limits their practicality for routine design studies and transient analyses. Deterministic methods, such as DYN3D [5], offer much faster solutions using simplified forms of the neutron transport equation but depend strongly on the accuracy of the homogenized few-group cross-section data they employ.

In compact SMR cores, strong neutron leakage and pronounced spectral neutron flux gradients make standard homogenization techniques less reliable [6]. Serpent is commonly used for generating multigroup libraries for nodal simulations; however, the use of OpenMC for this purpose has been far more limited. OpenMC offers several advantages compared with Serpent—its fully open-source nature, high level of customizability, Python API, active development, advanced acceleration techniques, and a large, supportive user community. Therefore, we explore how suitable OpenMC is for the generation of few-group cross-section libraries for nodal calculations.

This work establishes an OpenMC-to-DYN3D workflow for a NuScale-like SMR benchmark. OpenMC is used to generate a dedicated cross-section library for DYN3D, enabling consistent comparisons between stochastic and deterministic results at assembly, mini-core, and full-core levels. The study evaluates the sources of discrepancy between the two methods and highlights the need for advanced homogenization improvements, such as B1 spectral correction and ADFs, to enhance deterministic accuracy in SMR analyses.

2. Benchmark Specification

The reactor model used in this study is based on the NuScale-like SMR benchmark [7, 8]. The core comprises 37 fuel assemblies (FAs) of seven distinct types, characterized by varying U-235 enrichment and the presence of Gd_2O_3 burnable poison, as shown in Figure 1. Each FA follows a standard 17×17 lattice configuration, containing 264 fuel rods and 24 guide tubes. Four of the assembly types incorporate 16 Gd_2O_3 bearing fuel pins; in particular, assembly C02 corresponds to 4.55 wt% U-235 enrichment with integrated gadolinium burnable absorber, with a total gadolinium atomic number density of $2.70270 \times 10^{-3} \text{ barn}^{-1} \cdot \text{cm}^{-1}$, as specified in the benchmark definition [7]. The fuel rod pitch within an assembly is 1.2598 cm, and the assembly pitch within the core is 21.5036 cm. A high-fidelity OpenMC model of this core, which serves as the reference solution for this work, has been previously developed and validated [8, 9].

Figure 1. Radial view of the OpenMC NuScale-like core. The different colors shown in the legend represent fuel assemblies with varying U-235 enrichments and Gd₂O₃ content.

3. OpenMC Cross-Section Generation

Generating a high-quality cross-section library is crucial for the accuracy of DYN3D simulations. In this work, OpenMC was selected for this task due to its high-fidelity treatment of neutron transport, flexibility in handling complex geometries, and status as a modern, open-source platform [4].

3.1. Methodology and Workflow

The first step was to perform flux-weighted homogenization of microscopic cross-sections at the fuel assembly level using the OpenMC multigroup cross-section (MGXS) capability [10], and collapsing them into a two-energy-group structure [0, 0.625 eV, 20 MeV]. The tallied macroscopic cross-sections included transport, absorption, nu-fission, kappa-fission, scatter matrix, chi, inverse velocity, decay rate, and delayed neutron fractions. The diffusion coefficients supplied to DYN3D were calculated from the

transport cross section as $D_g = \frac{1}{3\Sigma_{tr,g}}$, consistent with P_1 transport-corrected diffusion theory [10]. The same procedure was applied to the core reflector regions.

To capture operational feedback effects, cross-sections were generated over a range of state variables:

- Fuel temperatures (K): 300, 900, 1200, 1500, 2100
- Coolant densities (g/cm^3): 0.65, 0.7, 0.74, 0.88, 1.0
- Boron concentrations (ppm): 0, 1000, 2000

A full combinatorial set of these parameters required 75 unique OpenMC simulations per fuel assembly type. All cross sections were generated for fresh (0-burnup) fuel, as burnup effects were not considered in this study. To ensure reproducibility of the generated cross-section libraries, identical boundary conditions were applied in both OpenMC and DYN3D models, and a fixed random seed was used in all OpenMC simulations. Parallel executions were verified to produce consistent cross-section values and statistical uncertainties across repeated runs.

3.2. Optimization via Geometric Symmetry

To optimize computational efficiency, a study on geometric symmetry was conducted. A simulation of the full A01 fuel assembly required 35 hours on a high-performance computing cluster for 75 runs, utilizing 200,000 neutron histories per cycle across 100 inactive and 320 active cycles. The calculation was executed on a single node equipped with AMD EPYC 9634 processors (168 cores, 1.5 TB RAM), with OpenMC employing 40 physical cores operating at ~ 3.7 GHz (~ 147 GHz aggregate throughput). This configuration yielded a multiplication factor (k_{eff}) of 0.96382 ± 10 pcm and an average relative uncertainty in the fast-group scattering cross-section of 0.08%.

Subsequently, a model applying $\frac{1}{8}$ FA symmetry of the A01 assembly was developed Figure 2. By evaluating several simulation configurations, the approach employing 25,000 neutron histories per cycle with 200 inactive and 2,500 active cycles substantially improved computational efficiency by 32%, reducing the overall runtime while maintaining comparable accuracy, with a k_{eff} standard deviation of 11 pcm and a fast-group scattering uncertainty of 0.08%.

Figure 2. Application of symmetry in modeling the A01 fuel assembly using OpenMC, showing the full geometry and its $\frac{1}{8}$ symmetric segment with reflective boundary conditions.

This optimization strategy, applicable across different computing platforms, enables the generation of more detailed cross-section libraries (e.g., with a finer parameter grid or additional state variables) within the same computational budget, thereby enhancing the potential accuracy and range of applicability of the subsequent DYN3D model.

4. DYN3D Model and Comparative Analysis

A full-core DYN3D model of the NuScale-like SMR was developed, as shown in Figure 3, using the OpenMC-generated cross-section library for all deterministic calculations. The deterministic calculations were performed using the 3D two-group nodal diffusion solver implemented in DYN3D. The OpenMC reference solutions were obtained using 1,000,000 particles per batch over 2,700 total batches, including 200 inactive cycles. Model accuracy was evaluated by comparing DYN3D predictions with OpenMC results across increasing levels of geometric complexity, from single assemblies to the full core.

Figure 3. Radial view of the DYN3D NuScale-like core. The different colors shown in the legend represent fuel assemblies with varying U-235 enrichments and the reflector.

4.1. Model Development

Initial validation was performed on single fuel assembly models with vacuum boundary conditions applied vertically and reflective radially, as presented in Figure 4A. The results, summarized in Table I, showed good agreement, with eigenvalue differences ranging from 124 pcm to 326 pcm for different assembly types.

Figure 4. Axial and radial views of the DYN3D model. (A) A01 fuel assembly with top and bottom reflectors. (B) 3x3 mini-core of A01, A02, and C03 assemblies. Reflective (R) and vacuum (V) boundaries are applied.

Table I. Comparison of k_{eff} values calculated by DYN3D and OpenMC for each fuel assembly type under identical boundary conditions.

FA	DYN3D k_{eff}	OpenMC k_{eff}	Variation ($ X1 - X2 * 10^5$) (pcm)
A01	0.95403	0.95498 ± 0.00002	94
A02	0.97919	0.97868 ± 0.00002	51
B01	1.13557	1.13274 ± 0.00002	283
B02	1.14857	1.14520 ± 0.00002	337
C01	1.27151	1.27149 ± 0.00002	2
C02	1.12881	1.12843 ± 0.00002	38
C03	1.14857	1.14520 ± 0.00002	337

A 3×3 mini-core configuration was modeled as shown in Figure 4B. The agreement remained strong, with an eigenvalue difference of 95 pcm. The OpenMC reference calculation for this case yielded a k_{eff} of 0.99163 ± 0.00002 . The normalized radial power distribution at the assembly level showed a maximum Relative Percentage Difference (RPD) of approximately 2% for most assemblies, with a localized peak of 6.37% in the central, highest-power assembly (Tables II & III). This deviation is primarily related to the strong flux and spectral gradients around the central high-power assembly, which increase the sensitivity of the two-group homogenized parameters in the nodal diffusion model. The relative Monte Carlo statistical uncertainty (1σ) of the assembly power tallies was below 0.3% for all assemblies. Slight asymmetries between geometrically equivalent positions were observed, primarily due to statistical noise inherent in MC codes [8]. Additional high-statistics calculations reported in [8], using increased particle histories and a larger number of active batches, confirmed that these residual asymmetries remain within the statistical uncertainty of the reference solution.

Table II. Calculated normalized radial power distribution at the fuel assembly level for a 3×3 core configuration with all control rods withdrawn.

	DYN3D			OpenMC			
	A	B	C	A	B	C	
1	0.9281	0.9342	0.9281	1	0.9472	0.9403	0.9466
2	0.9342	1.5508	0.9342	2	0.9401	1.4521	0.9399
3	0.9281	0.9342	0.9281	3	0.9469	0.9398	0.9471

Table III. Relative Percentage Difference (RPD) between DYN3D and OpenMC results for normalized radial power distribution at the fuel assembly level for a 3×3 core configuration with all control rods withdrawn.

Relative Percentage Difference (RPD)			
$ T1 - T2 / (T1) * 100\%$			
	A	B	C
1	2.0579	0.6479	1.9888
2	0.6356	6.3666	0.6140
3	2.0215	0.6046	2.049

4.2. Full-Core Analysis and Discrepancies

The full-core calculations were performed under a static isothermal configuration, with uniform fuel temperature of 900 K, moderator density of 0.800 g/cm³, and boron concentration of 1000 ppm. For the full 37-assembly core, the normalized radial power distribution exhibited significant deviations, as summarized in Table IV and Table V. The comparison revealed an eigenvalue difference of about 15869 pcm, with local RPDs reaching around 66% in some assemblies. These discrepancies arise not only from strong neutron leakage and steep flux gradients but also from limitations in the homogenization process, spectral inconsistencies between assemblies, reflector treatment errors, and the loss of heterogeneous interface information during group condensation. Additional contributors include inaccuracies in modeling axial discontinuities, simplified boundary conditions, and the absence of transport-corrected diffusion parameters, all of which become more pronounced in compact SMR geometries.

Table IV. Calculated normalized radial power distribution at the fuel assembly level for a Full core configuration with all control rods withdrawn.

DYN3D							OpenMC						
A	B	C	D	E	F	G	A	B	C	D	E	F	G
1		1.6375	1.1357	1.6375			1		1.0800	1.0045	1.0790		
2	1.3065	1.1175	0.5441	1.1175	1.3065		2	0.9762	1.1713	0.8755	1.1707	0.9747	
3	1.6375	1.1175	0.4008	0.2639	0.4008	1.1175	3	1.0796	1.1718	0.8607	0.7767	0.8601	1.1697
4	1.1357	0.5441	0.2639	0.3553	0.2639	0.5441	4	1.0031	0.8746	0.7767	1.0433	0.7763	0.8740
5	1.6375	1.1175	0.4008	0.2639	0.4008	1.1175	5	1.0782	1.1706	0.8607	0.7764	0.8607	1.1703
6	1.3065	1.1175	0.5441	1.1175	1.3065		6	0.9748	1.1703	0.8746	1.1703	0.9753	
7		1.6375	1.1357	1.6375			7		1.0784	1.0036	1.0786		

Table V. Relative Percentage Difference (RPD) between DYN3D and OpenMC results for normalized radial power distribution at the fuel assembly level for a Full core configuration with all control rods withdrawn.

Relative Percentage Difference (RPD)						
$ T1-T2 /(T1) *100\%$						
A	B	C	D	E	F	G
1		51.6181	13.0580	51.7617		
2	33.8367	4.5953	37.8511	4.5428	34.0392	
3	51.6743	4.6338	53.4355	66.0246	53.4021	4.4663
4	13.2136	37.7904	66.0218	65.9460	66.0054	37.7488
5	51.8791	4.5346	53.4315	66.0094	53.4323	4.5105
6	34.0212	4.5115	37.7884	4.5148	33.9599	
7		51.8410	13.1571	51.8147		

To mitigate these effects, B1 spectral corrections were applied to account for leakage-induced spectrum hardening, followed by the implementation of ADFs to restore interface flux continuity between homogenized nodes. The B1 method introduces a buckling-dependent spectral correction to account for finite-system leakage effects in few-group diffusion calculations [11], while ADFs compensate for interface homogenization errors consistent with modern nodal methodologies outlined by Fridman et al. [12]. With the combined application of B1 correction and ADFs, the agreement with OpenMC improves substantially: the eigenvalue deviation is reduced to 101 pcm, and the maximum assembly-level RPD decreases from ~66% to below ~11%, with central assemblies exhibiting deviations below ~2%, as summarized in Table VI and Table VII

Table VI. Calculated normalized radial power distribution at the fuel assembly level for a full core configuration with all control rods withdrawn after applying B1 spectral correction and ADFs.

DYN3D							OpenMC						
A	B	C	D	E	F	G	A	B	C	D	E	F	G
1		1.0342	1.0272	1.0342			1		1.0800	1.0045	1.0790		
2	0.8709	1.2445	0.9037	1.2445	0.8709		2	0.9762	1.1713	0.8755	1.1707	0.9747	
3	1.0342	1.2445	0.8659	0.7617	0.8659	1.2445	3	1.0796	1.1718	0.8607	0.7767	0.8601	1.1697
4	1.0272	0.9037	0.7617	1.0524	0.7617	0.9037	4	1.0031	0.8746	0.7767	1.0433	0.7763	0.8740
5	1.0342	1.2445	0.8659	0.7617	0.8659	1.2445	5	1.0782	1.1706	0.8607	0.7764	0.8607	1.1703
6		0.8709	1.2445	0.9037	1.2445	0.8709	6		0.9748	1.1703	0.8746	1.1703	0.9753
7		1.0342	1.0272	1.0342			7		1.0784	1.0036	1.0786		

Table VII. Relative Percentage Difference (RPD) between DYN3D and OpenMC results for normalized radial power distribution at the fuel assembly level for a full core configuration with all control rods withdrawn after B1 and ADF corrections..

Relative Percentage Difference (RPD)						
$ T1-T2 /(T1) *100\%$						
A	B	C	D	E	F	G
1		4.2421	2.2569	4.1515		
2	10.7857	6.2470	3.2235	6.3055	10.6508	
3	4.2066	6.2042	0.5992	1.9360	0.6715	6.3908
4	2.3976	3.3243	1.9281	0.8680	1.8808	3.3935
5	4.0773	6.3147	0.6078	1.8921	0.6062	6.3415
6		10.6628	6.3404	3.3277	6.3367	10.7036
7		4.1013	2.3465	4.1180		

5. CONCLUSIONS

This work established a workflow for generating high-fidelity OpenMC-based cross sections for DYN3D and applied it to a NuScale-like SMR. While assembly and mini-core results showed good agreement, full-core simulations initially exhibited large deviations in reactivity (~15869 pcm) and power distribution (up to 66% RPD) due to spectral and homogenization effects in the compact SMR geometry. The implementation of B1 spectral correction and ADFs significantly reduced these discrepancies, improving the eigenvalue difference to 101 pcm and substantially enhancing radial power agreement. Further improvements are expected through refined reflector modeling and consistent treatment of reflector–core interface conditions. These results demonstrate that properly corrected deterministic models can achieve high accuracy while maintaining computational efficiency for SMR core analysis.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Matthews, J.; Bodell, W.; Butler, G. Nuclear Cogeneration to Support a Net-Zero, High-Renewable Electricity Grid. *Energies* 2024, 17, 6219. [Google Scholar]
- [2] Vaya Soler, A.; Berthelemy, M.; Verma, A.; Bilbao y Leon, S.; Kwong, G.; Sozoniuk, V.; White, A.; Rouyer, V.; Sexton Nick, K.; Vasquez-Maignan, X.; et al. Small Modular Reactors: Challenges and Opportunities; Nuclear Energy Agency of the OECD (NEA): Boulogne-Billancourt, France, 2021. [Google Scholar]
- [3] Zhang, H.; Mousseau, V.; Zhao, H. Development of a High Fidelity System Analysis Code for Generation IV Reactors; Idaho National Laboratory (INL): Idaho Falls, ID, USA, 2008. [Google Scholar]
- [4] Romano, P.K.; Horelik, N.E.; Herman, B.R.; Nelson, A.G.; Forget, B.; Smith, K. OpenMC: A state-of-the-art Monte Carlo code for research and development. *Ann. Nucl. Energy* 2015, 82, 90–97. [Google Scholar]
- [5] Grundmann, U.; Rohde, U.; Mittag, S. DYN3D-Three-Dimensional Core Model for Steady-State and Transient Analysis of Thermal Reactors-155; American Nuclear Society: La Grange Park, IL, USA, 2000. [Google Scholar]
- [6] Rader, J.; Godfrey, A.; Graham, A.; Lietwiler, C.; Smith, H.; Saia, M. Comparisons of Nodal Diffusion and Whole-Core Transport Methods for Multiple Cycles of a Small Light Water Reactor; Oak Ridge National Laboratory (ORNL): Oak Ridge, TN, USA, 2022.
- [7] Fridman, E.; Bilodid, Y.; Valtavirta, V. Definition of the neutronics benchmark of the NuScale-like core. *Nucl. Eng. Technol.* 2023, 55, 3639–3647. [Google Scholar]
- [8] Ez Aldeen, A., Litskevich, D., Grove, C., Atkinson, S., Detkina, A., & Gulzar, H. Simulation of NuScale-Like SMR Benchmark with OpenMC Code. *Journal of Nuclear Engineering*. 2025, 6(4), 44. Available online: <https://doi.org/10.3390/jne6040044>
- [9] Ez Aldeen, A. Simulation Data for NuScale-Like SMR Benchmark with OpenMC Code. 2025. Available online: <https://zenodo.org/records/15231335> (accessed on 24 October 2025).
- [10] Boyd, W., Nelson, A., Romano, P.K., Shaner, S., Forget, B., & Smith, K. (2019). Multigroup cross-section generation with the OpenMC Monte Carlo particle transport code. *Nuclear Technology*, 205(7), 928–944. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00295450.2019.1571828>
- [11] R.J. Stammler and M.J. Abbate, *Methods of Steady-State Reactor Physics in Nuclear Design*, Academic Press, London (1983).
- [12] Fridman E, Smith JD, Kotlyar D. Insights into calculating Reference Discontinuity Factors with Serpent Monte Carlo code. *Annals of Nuclear Energy*. 2025 Feb 1;211:110997. Available online: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anucene.2024.110997>